

Preparation of Electrolyte-Free Sol of Manganese Dioxide.

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Gorgeu (*Ann. Chim. phys.*, 1862, 66, 155), Spring and de Boeck (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1887, 48, 170) obtained colloidal manganese dioxide in electrolyte-free condition by washing a freshly precipitated sample with conductivity water. The colloid-content of the sol was poor. The method adopted by most of the subsequent workers has been either the reduction of potassium permanganate or oxidation of a suitable manganese salt. This procedure introduces into the system appreciable traces of some electrolyte. Attempts at removing the electrolytes by dialysis result in the precipitation of the colloid on the dialysing septum. (*cf. Cuy, J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 415; Ganguly and Dhar, *ibid.*, 1922, 26, 701). The following experiments were carried out to obtain further information about this behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fairly stable suspensions were obtained by (i) careful oxidation of manganese sulphate by bromine and (ii) reduction of permanganate by (a) formaldehyde, (b) ethyl acetate, (c) alcohol and similar agents. These methods were considered unsatisfactory, because of the residual electrolyte in (i) and possible formation of complex organic salts in (ii). The most satisfactory method was the reduction of potassium permanganate by concentrated ammonia, added drop by drop (*Cuy, loc. cit.*). Cataphoretic experiments showed that the sols were always negatively charged.

The sol used in the following experiments was prepared by the last method. In agreement with previous workers (*cf. Cuy, loc. cit.*), we found that the residual KOH had but little coagulating effect. Small amounts of even a moderately concentrated solution of KOH however precipitated the colloid. The sol coagulated slowly, when brought into contact with unglazed porcelain, animal charcoal, celluloid, glass-wool, filter and parchment papers. The course

of dialysis of the colloid with a negative potential applied to the dialysing septum was next investigated. The positive terminal of either the D. C. mains or of a battery of storage cells was earthed and the negative terminal was connected to a number of turns of platinum wire wound round the parchment sac, which was tied from one end of a well-cleaned glass tube and immersed in twice-distilled water. The volume of the sac was always greater than that of the sol, so as to avoid contact with the glass tube in view of the observed instabilising influence of glass. The results observed in one typical series of experiments are given below. These relate the magnitude of the negative potential with the time, during which a constant volume of the sol (10 c. c.) was observed to be stable in the dialyser.

Potential applied (volts).	0	6.5	10.5	24.0	52.0	220.0
Time (min.).	30	50	60	144	180	above 18 hrs.

It was found that after dialysing for about 18 hours, no sensible amount of KOH could be detected, when the sol after concentration to a very small volume by boiling, was tested with litmus. The possibility of the presence of free ammonia in the sol is excluded, as it would escape during boiling for concentration. Since in the preparation of the sol, ammonia was added drop by drop to a large excess of a boiling permanganate solution, and since the sol was further boiled before being stocked, and the alkalinity of the sol was perceptible only after concentration by boiling, any free ammonia could be present only in trace. Prolongation of the dialysis after the above stage induced a slow but sensible coagulation. We have found it possible to obviate this by use of still greater negative potentials. The resulting sol was much more sensitive to electrolytes.

Discussion.

It is seen that the stability of the colloid increases rapidly with applied potential. In an experiment, a positive potential of 200 volts was applied, and the whole colloid coagulated in about 10 minutes, as compared with 30 minutes with no potential applied.

The stabilising influence of the negative potential is apparently connected with the negative charge of the colloid, as its deposition on the dialyser would be to some extent counteracted by electric repulsion.

It was found that the same sol could be rendered electrolyte-free by hot dialysis. It follows therefore that the tendency of the sol to coagulate in ordinary dialysis cannot be appreciably due to any chemical interaction between the colloid and the dialyser material, since this would increase with temperature. It is known that coagulating tendency and adsorption are intimately connected, and that the latter diminishes with temperature. The increased stability of the colloid during hot dialysis may therefore be ascribed to the corresponding diminution in the adsorption of the colloid by the parchment. In hot dialysis, there is a possibility of peptisation (at any rate, contamination) of the colloid by traces of the dialyser material, disintegrated at the high temperature. Furthermore, factors like the size of the colloid particles, the stability of the sol might be affected during the process of hot dialysis. Evidence regarding this is afforded in the behaviour of the arsenious sulphide sol on heating (Kruyt and Spek, *Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 25, 1; also, Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 350), and in the decomposing tendency of the uranium ferrocyanide sol under conditions of hot dialysis (Gore and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 648). None of these factors are present under the conditions of dialysis in the cold used here. Results of a detailed investigation, now in progress, examining the applicability of the present method to other colloids will be published in a later communication.

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